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Van der Waals WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure as a visible-light photodetector and pressure optoelectronic sensor

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Abstract

Two-dimensional van der Waals heterostructures offer a versatile platform for developing multifunctional optoelectronic devices, as their tuneable electronic and optical properties enable a wide range of applications. Among them, WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructures exhibit attractive features, making them promising candidates for the realization of broadband photodetectors and pressure optoelectronic sensors. In this study, WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructures were fabricated and electrically characterized under different environmental and light conditions. WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructures exhibit n-type conduction with an impressive ON/OFF current ratio up to 10⁸, demonstrating their suitability for high-performance electronic devices. Their electrical properties were extensively investigated under different pressure conditions, from ambient pressure to high vacuum (10³ to 10⁻⁴ mbar), both in the dark and under illumination. The results reveal that the adsorption and desorption of water and oxygen molecules on the materials' surface play a crucial role in modulating the electrical response of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure. Analysis of the light response in the visible spectrum reveals a responsivity of up to 1.2 A/W at a wavelength of 620 nm. WS₂/PdSe₂-based devices were further tested as pressure optoelectronic sensors, monitoring the photocurrent evolution during transitions between high vacuum and ambient pressure. These findings open the way for various applications in the field of optoelectronics and sensing.

Introduction

In the last decades, two-dimensional (2D) materials like transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) and black phosphorus (bP) have gained significant attention due to their unique properties¹. The absence of dangling bonds, the strong light-matter interaction and the bandgap tunability make 2D materials

ideal for electronic and optoelectronic applications. However, achieving environmental stability and high carrier mobility remains critical for their integration into real-world devices. TMDs, such as MoS_2 , WS_2 , MoSe_2 , and WSe_2 , exhibit good air stability under ambient conditions but often suffer from relatively low charge carrier mobility.²⁻⁸ In contrast, bP offers exceptionally high mobilities, reaching up to $1000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ^{9,10}, but its susceptibility to air-induced degradation due to oxidation significantly hampers its electrical performance.¹¹⁻¹³

The development of 2D van der Waals (vdW) heterostructures has been a significant turning point in materials science and nanotechnology, allowing the creation of devices with superior performance by combining the more intriguing properties of several materials.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ High-quality flakes can be produced by mechanically exfoliating bulk crystals.^{18,19} These flakes can then be assembled by hand stacking, depending on the vdW forces acting between layers without the need for lattice matching, to create thin, atomically sharp heterointerfaces that are essential for high-quality device performance.²⁰

Tungsten disulfide (WS_2) presents a hexagonal crystal structure, and a direct bandgap that ranges from 1.3 to 2.0 eV passing from the bulk crystal to the monolayer sheet.^{21,22} As most of TMDs, its carrier mobility in standard conditions is in the range $0.01\text{-}10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.²³⁻²⁵ Since wide bandgap 2D materials tend to exhibit longer carrier lifetimes and reduced recombination probability, which is highly advantageous in optoelectronics^{26,27}, WS_2 -based devices have been widely explored for electronic and optoelectronic applications, including light-emitting diodes (LEDs), laser, optical modulators, and photodetectors with significant impact in various fields.²⁸⁻³¹ Yan et al.³² fabricated memristors using WS_2 flakes, achieving fast switching times and low program currents in the ON state. WS_2 has also been employed in the fabrication of multiple heterostructures, enabling the development of broadband photodetectors, such as WS_2/Si – based devices.^{33,34} D. Kwak et al.³⁵ demonstrated a multilayer WS_2/bP heterostructure for high-performance photovoltaic applications, achieving a rectification ratio of 10^3 , an external quantum efficiency of 4.4% and a solar efficiency of 4.6%. Additionally, the anisotropy of monolayer WS_2 , combined with the in-plane anisotropy of bP, was leveraged to form a WS_2/bP heterojunction with an anisotropic ratio of 1.84 for neutral excitons, demonstrating potential for anisotropic optoelectronic applications.³⁶

Identifying materials for vdW heterostructures that combine stability, high mobility, and enhanced optoelectronic properties is therefore crucial for advancing device performance. Palladium diselenide (PdSe_2) is a noble metal-based TMD with a unique pentagonal crystal structure, setting it apart from most of 2D materials. It is characterized by high charge carrier mobility, more than $100 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and demonstrates remarkable stability in ambient conditions over extended periods.³⁷⁻⁴⁰ With its wide range of thickness-dependent bandgap tunability and excellent air stability, PdSe_2 is a strong candidate for broadband photodetection.^{41,42} In this context, WS_2 , as a wide-bandgap semiconductor, and PdSe_2 , as a narrow-bandgap material, can be effectively integrated to form a type I heterojunction, where both electrons and holes are confined within the PdSe_2 layer. This band alignment supports efficient radiative recombination and may be advantageous for light-emitting applications. Therefore, the combination of WS_2 and PdSe_2 in vertical structures enables the formation of vdW heterostructures that combine the advantageous aspects of both materials: the wide, tuneable, and direct bandgap of WS_2 together with the high mobility and narrow bandgap of PdSe_2 . Furthermore, both materials exhibit good environmental stability over time, which is crucial for real-world applications. As a result, the $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterostructure holds great promise for

advanced electronic and optoelectronic devices, including field-effect transistors (FETs), photodetectors, photovoltaic devices, and sensors. T. Chen et al.⁴³ leveraged the tuneable polarity of a $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure to demonstrate its use as a reconfigurable rectifier, achieving rectification ratios ranging from 10^{-4} to 10^4 . They also developed a logic inverter based on the dual-mode rectification capability of serially connected $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures. Furthermore, $PdSe_2$ thin films were decorated with WS_2 nanoparticles to enhance their gas-sensing capabilities, leveraging the catalytic effect and n-type doping introduced by the WS_2 nanoparticles. Gas sensors based on $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures exhibit approximately 2.8 times greater sensitivity and improved selectivity compared to pristine $PdSe_2$.⁴⁴

In this work, we report the fabrication and the electrical and optoelectronic characterization of $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures. We have investigated the electrical and optoelectronic properties of the mentioned heterostructures as a function of pressure, emphasizing the role of the adsorption and desorption of water (H_2O) and/or oxygen (O_2) molecules. Electrical measurements were conducted initially at ambient pressure, then in a high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar and finally repeated in ambient conditions to analyse the reversibility of the pressure-dependent processes. Additionally, the photoconductivity of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures was thoroughly studied across the visible wavelength range and wider pressure range, from 10^3 to 10^{-4} mbar, and back. Measurements sequences in air, vacuum and air again, both in dark and under illumination, demonstrate the reversibility of the adsorption and desorption processes. In addition to the promising optical properties of $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures for visible-light photodetectors, their long-term air stability and high sensitivity to H_2O and O_2 molecules make them ideal candidates for pressure optoelectronic sensors, as these factors significantly influence their photoresponse.

2. Materials and Methods

Electrodes were patterned via a maskless lithography system (SmartForce SmartPrint) and deposited by thermal evaporation of 5 nm Cr (adhesion layer) and 45 nm Au on n^{++} -Si/ SiO_2 (290 nm oxide thickness) substrates. Firstly, WS_2 flakes, and then $PdSe_2$ flakes, were mechanically exfoliated with scotch tape from bulk crystals onto polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamps. Then, the surface of the PDMS stamps was inspected through an optical microscope in transmission mode to identify high-quality and homogeneous flakes via optical contrast.⁴⁵ The optical images of the flakes onto the PDMS stamps are reported in Figure S1a-b in the Supporting Information. Once a WS_2 flake was selected, an all-dry deterministic transfer was used to correctly place the flake onto the prepatterned substrate, with a portion of the flake in contact with the gold (see Fig. S1c, Supporting Information).⁴⁶ Subsequently, a $PdSe_2$ flake was selected using the same procedure and transferred onto the substrate with WS_2 , resulting in an overlap of the two layered materials. Figure 1a shows an optical image of a device of the batch described above. A home-built setup was used for flakes' transfer, and PDMS stamps were used as carriers.²⁰ Figure 1b displays a schematic of a device under examination, showing that $PdSe_2$ side serves as the source, while the WS_2 part acts as the drain. The highly doped Si substrate, covered by conductive silver paste, constitutes the back-gate electrode. The drain and gate voltages, V_{ds} and V_{gs} , respectively, were swept to monitor the drain current (I_d). Figure 1c shows an atomic force microscope (AFM) image of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure, acquired on a scan area of $40\ \mu m \times 40\ \mu m$. Multiple profiles were extracted from this image (see Figure S2, Supporting Information, to see the region of the flake from which they were extracted) and the thickness of the single WS_2 and $PdSe_2$ flakes was estimated (see Figure 1d).

Figure 1e presents the photoluminescence (PL) from PdSe₂ (green), WS₂ (blue), and the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterojunction (red) at ambient pressure and temperature. The absent photoluminescence (PL) intensity of PdSe₂ is due to its indirect bandgap, while WS₂ presents a broad peak at 1.95 eV. A significant PL quenching from the region of the WS₂/PdSe₂ overlap can be observed. The PL peak intensity in the WS₂/PdSe₂ region decreases to 66% of that of single WS₂, which can be attributed to exciton dissociation and charge transfer at the heterojunction interface. Additionally, the laser penetrating the PdSe₂ sheets loses part of its energy, contributing to the decrease in the final PL peak intensity of WS₂.

Raman spectra of the single materials and the heterojunction were acquired under laser excitation of 532 nm and are reported in Figure 1f. The red profile corresponds to the Raman spectrum from WS₂/PdSe₂ overlapping region. Peaks at around 350 cm⁻¹ and 417 cm⁻¹ correspond to the in-plane optical mode E_{2g}¹ of WS₂ and out-of-plane vibrations, A_{1g}, of sulphur atoms, respectively. Despite the measured thickness (2.4 nm), the position of these two peaks suggests that the WS₂ flake is a monolayer.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹

The difference of the measured thickness to the nominal 0.6 nm of one layer of WS₂ can be attributed to process residues and ubiquitous water molecules.^{50,51} The monolayer nature of the WS₂ flake is also confirmed by the differential reflectance spectrum, measured while on the PDMS stamp, as shown in Figure S2c in the Supporting Information. Peaks at 140 cm⁻¹, 203 cm⁻¹, 219 cm⁻¹, and 255 cm⁻¹ are associated to A_g¹, A_g², B_{1g}², and A_g³ modes of PdSe₂, respectively. The position of peaks confirm the multilayer structure of the PdSe₂ flake.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ Since the PdSe₂ multilayers absorb part of the excitation power and Raman signal, the WS₂ signal in the overlapped part of the heterojunction is weaker than the pure WS₂.⁵⁵ The Raman spectra confirm the formation of the heterojunction, and the high quality of the single flakes and the overlapped region at the interface.

Figure 1: (a) Optical image of a $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterostructure. (b) Schematic of the back-gated device based on $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterojunction with the electrical measurement setup. (c) AFM image of a $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterostructure acquired on a scan area of $40\ \mu\text{m} \times 40\ \mu\text{m}$. The colour scale ranges from 0 to 450 nm. (d) AFM profiles of the WS_2 (left graph) and PdSe_2 (right graph) flakes. (e) Photoluminescence and (f) Raman spectra of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterojunction (red), single WS_2 (blue) and PdSe_2 (green) flakes.

2. Results and discussion

Before investigating the electrical behaviour of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure under dark and ambient conditions, the electrical conduction of single WS₂ and PdSe₂-based FETs was analysed. Then, the impact of air exposure on WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructures was examined by repeating the same electrical measurements while reducing the air pressure to 10⁻⁴ mbar to remove air molecules. The reversibility of air molecule adsorption was analysed by repeating the measurements under ambient conditions again. The device based on the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterojunction was tested as a pressure optoelectronic sensor by evaluating its photoresponse across a wide pressure range, from 10⁻⁴ to 10³ mbar.

The electrical measurements were carried out in two-probe configuration, as schematized in Figure 1b, using a LakeShore probe station with an integrated optical fiber, connected to a Keithley 4200 semiconductor characterization system, having a current and voltage sensitivity of about 0.1 pA and 2 μV, respectively. All the measurements were conducted at room temperature.

2.1 Electrical characterization (dark condition)

Figure 2a-b show the transfer curves, that is, the channel current as a function of V_{gs} at a fixed V_{ds}, of WS₂ and PdSe₂ devices. Such curves are from devices based on single WS₂ and PdSe₂ flakes, fabricated with the same procedure used for the heterostructure; their optical images are shown in Figure S1e-f (Supporting Information). WS₂ presents n-type conduction with low carrier mobility, both at ambient pressure and in high vacuum at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mbar. In contrast, PdSe₂ shows ambipolar conduction with electron and hole mobilities within the same interval of values at ambient pressure and transitions to n-type conduction when H₂O and O₂ molecules are removed from the surface. The field-effect mobility, μ_{eff}, is calculated using the following equation

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = \frac{L}{C_{\text{ox}} V_{\text{ds}} W} \frac{dI_{\text{d}}}{dV_{\text{gs}}}$$

where L and W are the channel length and width, respectively, C_{ox} = 1.15 × 10⁻⁸ F cm⁻² is the oxide capacitance for 290 nm of SiO₂, and $\frac{dI_{\text{d}}}{dV_{\text{gs}}}$ is the transconductance of the linear part of the transfer curve in the on-state. The field-effect mobility in WS₂ is around 0.01 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ and becomes 5.00 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ in high vacuum, while for PdSe₂, the electron mobility passes from 24 to 63 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ and the hole mobility passes from 39 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ to 10 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹, lowering the pressure from 10³ to 10⁻⁴ mbar. The combination of high charge carrier mobility of PdSe₂ and unipolar conductive behaviour of WS₂ results in the formation of an intriguing vdW heterostructure based on WS₂/PdSe₂ that can be exploited for their unique electrical and optical properties.

Figure 2c illustrates the current of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure as a function of V_{ds} between -10 and 10 V, with a grounded gate. The system undergoes three states: the initial state at ambient pressure (n = 1, solid black line), an intermediate state under high vacuum at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mbar (n = 3, solid red line), and the final state after returning to ambient pressure (n = 5, dashed black line). The solid black curve reproduces the electrical behaviour of the device at ambient pressure, n = 1. As the pressure decreases to 10⁻⁴ mbar, O₂ and H₂O molecules desorb from the surface of the materials, leading to a significant increase in current, surpassing 1 μA at V_{ds} = ±10 V. Additionally, the

I_d - V_{ds} characteristic becomes less asymmetric (solid red curve), with the current ratio ($I_{d,-10V}/I_{d,10V}$) evolving from 200 at ambient pressure to 4 in high vacuum. Notably, the I_d - V_{ds} characteristic goes back to its initial configuration (dashed black curve) once the chamber returns to ambient pressure. This behaviour underscores the pronounced sensitivity of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure to adsorbed species.

Figure 2d displays the transfer curves at a fixed $V_{ds} = 5$ V, for different system states. These states not only include $n = 1, 3, 5$ (as described previously), but also $n = 2$ (dotted red curve), which corresponds to high vacuum at 10^{-4} mbar before complete desorption, and $n = 4$ (dotted black curve), which corresponds to ambient pressure before complete adsorption. The transfer curves in all the states present typical n-type conduction, characterized by a higher current at positive V_{gs} and an off-state of the transistor in the region with more negative V_{gs} . The hysteresis width of the transfer curves, defined as the maximum gate voltage difference between the two branches of the curve, evolves gradually across the states from $n = 1$ to $n = 5$. It decreases from 70 V at ambient pressure ($n = 1$) to 15 V at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar ($n = 3$), as depicted in Figure S3 in the Supporting Information. This hysteresis width arises primarily from charge trapping at the interface between SiO_2 and the semiconductor materials, as well as residuals from fabrication processes. Indeed, H_2O molecules could contribute to the transfer of electrons from the trap states and/or provide extra traps by weakening some bonds in the top SiO_2 layers.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ The dramatic reduction (over 50%) in hysteresis width from $n = 1$ to $n = 3$ highlights the dominant role of adsorbates, whose adsorption at selenium and sulphur vacancy sites is favoured especially at positive V_{gs} . The ON/OFF current ratio, defined as the ratio between the maximum and minimum current of the transfer curves at different states ranges between 10^7 and 10^8 (see Figure S3, Supporting Information), showcasing a promising characteristic for electronic device applications. The lowest value of the ON/OFF current ratio is observed in high vacuum ($n = 3$), attributed to the leftward shift of the transfer curve caused by O_2 desorption. The achieved values are at least four orders of magnitude higher than the ones reported in the literature for similar devices.⁵⁹ Notably, the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure exhibits n-type conduction with a significantly enhanced ON/OFF current ratio compared to individual WS_2 and $PdSe_2$ devices. This is particularly advantageous for electronics applications: the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure shows a clear distinction between the ON and OFF states, unlike the $PdSe_2$ device, which shows ambipolar behaviour, making it more challenging to achieve sharp switching characteristics.

Figure 2e shows the transfer curves of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure at ambient pressure for different V_{ds} , ranging from -5 to 5 V, while sweeping the V_{gs} from 50 to -50 V, and back to 50 V. Similarly, Figure 2f presents the transfer curves at different V_{ds} (from -5 to 5 V) under a high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar. At ambient pressure, the transfer curves for positive and negative V_{ds} exhibit noticeable differences due to the significant asymmetry in the I_d - V_{ds} characteristics. In contrast, under high vacuum, the sets of transfer curves with V_{ds} ranging from 0 to 5 V and from 0 to -5 V appear much more similar, reflecting the symmetrisation of the I_d - V_{ds} characteristics.

Figure 2: Electrical measurements of single WS₂ and PdSe₂-based FETs and the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure in dark. Transfer curves at ambient pressure and in high vacuum at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mbar for single-flake devices based on (a) WS₂ and (b) PdSe₂. (c) I_d-V_{ds} characteristic of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure at ambient pressure (solid black line, n = 1), high vacuum at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mbar (solid red line, n = 3), and ambient pressure again (dashed black line, n = 5) with a grounded gate. (d) Transfer curves of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure at a fixed V_{ds} = 5 V in different states: at ambient pressure (solid black line, n = 1), high vacuum before complete desorption of molecules from the materials surface (dotted red line, n = 2), high vacuum at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mbar (solid red line, n = 3), ambient pressure soon after switching off the pumping system

before complete adsorption (dotted black line, $n = 4$), and ambient pressure (dashed black line, $n = 5$). Transfer curves of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterostructure with V_{ds} ranging from -5 to 5 V at (e) ambient pressure and in (f) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar.

2.2 Optoelectronic characterization (white light)

Time-resolved measurements were conducted by using a supercontinuum white laser (wavelength range: 450-2400 nm, Superk Compact, NKT Photonics). Laser pulses lasting 60 ns were acquired at $V_{ds} = \pm 5$ V to account for the asymmetric I_d - V_{ds} characteristics observed at ambient pressure. Figure 3a depicts the pulses at ambient pressure at $V_{ds} = -5$ V (top) and $V_{ds} = 5$ V (bottom) at increasing incident laser power (P_{inc} , $P_{inc} = P * S_{active}/S_{spot}$ with P the nominal laser power, S_{active} being the active area of the device and S_{spot} the area of the laser spot) from 48 to 241 μW , with the gate grounded. The photocurrent (I_{ph}), defined as the difference in current between the averaged current under light and the dark current (before illumination), depends on the incident laser power and follows a power law $I_{ph} \propto P_{inc}^\alpha$. The power law exponent α is 0.88 ± 0.06 at $V_{ds} = -5$ V and 0.71 ± 0.07 at $V_{ds} = 5$ V (see Figure 3b), consistently with what reported in the literature.⁵⁹ This sublinear relationship between I_{ph} and P_{inc} can be attributed to intricate mechanisms of photo-generated carriers during generation, trapping, and recombination processes.⁶⁰ Figure 3c shows time-dependent pulses measured in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar for $V_{ds} = -5$ V (top) and $V_{ds} = 5$ V (bottom). As previously mentioned, the I_d - V_{ds} characteristic becomes more symmetric as the pressure decreases, leading to photocurrent values at negative and positive voltage biases falling within the same range, (0.5 - 1.2) μA . In Figure 3d, the dependence of the photocurrent on the incident laser power continues to follow a power law, with α equal to 0.49 ± 0.08 at $V_{ds} = -5$ V and 0.55 ± 0.07 at $V_{ds} = 5$ V. The smaller values of α indicate a more pronounced sublinear regime in high vacuum.⁶¹

All the pulses acquired at ambient pressure (Figure 3a) were correctly fitted with a double exponential function, $I_d = I_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + A_2 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}}$, both for the rise and decay part (see Figure S4a, Supporting Information). The extracted τ_1 and τ_2 time constants, reported in Figure 3e, are on the order of 1 ns (0.2 ns) and 10 ns (10 ns) for the rise (decay) branch of the acquired light pulses at $V_{ds} = 5$ V at ambient pressure. The time constants correspond to the response time of the device to light, indicating the presence of two main mechanisms in the photogeneration: a faster one, associated to τ_1 , and a slower one, associated to τ_2 , which is at least ten times larger than τ_1 . Notably, the values of time constants τ_2 are still within a reasonable range for having high-speed optoelectronic devices. The electron-hole direct photogeneration presents fast response, probably limited by selenium vacancies in PdSe_2 and sulphur vacancies in WS_2 . The achieved photocurrent is due to a well-balanced contribution of the fast and slow mechanisms, as indicated by the ratio between the two amplitudes A_1 and A_2 , which is around 1 (see Figure S4b, Supporting Information).⁶² The A_1/A_2 ratio becomes much higher for the decay branch of the same pulses, from 10 to 100 passing from 48 to 241 μW for the incident laser power, indicating that the return to the dark state is dominated by the faster mechanism. We notice that the extracted time constants τ_1 and τ_2 are at least one order of magnitude lower than what reported in the literature for few-layer PdSe_2 -based photodetectors.⁶³ Actually, the photoresponse of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{PdSe}_2$ heterostructure is faster than other reported FETs based on MoS_2 , one of the most studied TMDs.^{61,64}

Figure 3: Time-resolved measurements of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure under white light illumination. 60 s long pulses at different incident laser powers at (a) ambient pressure and (c) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar at $V_{ds} = -5$ V (top) and $V_{ds} = 5$ V (bottom). Photocurrent as a function of the incident laser power on a logscale at (b) ambient pressure and (d) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar at $V_{ds} = -5$ V (coloured circles) and $V_{ds} = 5$ V (coloured squared). The power law exponent α is extracted from the linear fit of experimental data at $V_{ds} = -5$ V (violet line) and $V_{ds} = 5$ V (blue line). Time constants τ_1 and τ_2 from a double rise/decay

exponential fit of the time-resolved pulses at $V_{ds} = 5$ V at (e) ambient pressure and in a (f) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar.

The time-resolved light pulses in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar were also successfully fitted with a double exponential fit (see Figure S4c, Supporting Information). The rise branch is characterized by a τ_1 that is one order of magnitude smaller than the ones extracted at ambient pressure and τ_2 on the order of 10 s. The faster response is attributed to direct photogeneration. The decay branch of the same light pulses presents longer constant times because of the absence of adsorbates in high vacuum (see Figure 3f). The A_1/A_2 ratio remains around 1, indicating again a balanced contribution of both the mechanisms to the generation of photocurrent (see Figure S4d, Supporting Information). Figure S4e-f show the responsivity and specific detectivity of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure as a function of the incident laser power, both at ambient pressure and in high vacuum conditions.

The combination of $PdSe_2$ and WS_2 in the heterojunction results in shorter response times compared to single WS_2 -based FETs. Figure S5a and S5c (Supporting Information) show the time-dependent electrical signals of FETs based on single WS_2 flakes under white light illumination at ambient pressure and in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar. These pulses were fitted with single/double exponential functions, yielding time constants of up to 100 s (see Figure S5b-d). The higher mobility of $PdSe_2$ compared to WS_2 plays a key role in achieving shorter response times in $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures.⁶⁵

The electrical properties of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure under white light illumination were also investigated along with the application of a voltage bias on the gate electrode. Figure 4a shows the I_d - V_{ds} characteristics in dark (black line) and under illumination at varying incident white light powers (coloured lines) at ambient pressure, with the gate electrode grounded. Notably, the I_d - V_{ds} characteristic becomes more symmetric under illumination, although the current remains slightly higher at negative bias voltages compared to positive. The photoexcitation and photodesorption processes contribute to significantly reduce the Schottky barrier, leading to an increase in the current.⁶¹ Figure 4b presents the modulation of the channel current through transfer curves at a fixed $V_{ds} = 5$ V, with the gate voltage swept from 50 to -50 V and back to 50 V, both in dark (black line) and under illumination at various white light powers (coloured lines). At ambient pressure, the drain current under laser illumination is higher than in dark conditions at each gate voltage. The transfer curve maintains its shape during illumination, having higher current levels for both the off and the on states. In Figure 4c, the I_d - V_{ds} characteristics in dark (black line) and under illumination at varying incident white light powers (coloured lines) in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar are depicted. The more symmetric behaviour is maintained both in darkness and under laser. The difference between the dark and illuminated transfer curves gets more pronounced at negative gate voltages, and the transistor does not switch off when illuminated (see transfer curves in Figure 4d): the photoexcitation of electrons from the initial off state of the transistor results in a left-shift of the whole transfer curve, not allowing to see the off-state of the device within the same V_{gs} range.⁶⁶

The data of Figure 4b and 4d show that the gate is very effective in controlling the photoresponse. Negative V_{gs} results clearly advantageous to achieve a high signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 4: Electrical measurements of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure in dark and under white light illumination at (a-b) ambient pressure and in (c-d) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar.

2.3 Optoelectronic characterization (monochromatic light)

The light absorption of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterojunction was studied in the visible range by exposing the device to 60 seconds light pulses at fixed wavelengths. Light at a given wavelength was selected using a monochromator (Sciencetech Inc.) with a spectral bandwidth of 20 nm. Measurements were acquired in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar at a fixed $V_{ds} = 5$ V and $V_{gs} = -50$ V, a condition chosen to minimise the dark current (see Figure 4d, black curve). The photocurrent is displayed as a function of the light wavelength in Figure 5a. The responsivity, defined as the ratio between the photocurrent and the incident laser power at fixed wavelengths ($R = I_{ph}/P_{inc,\lambda}$), is maximum at $\lambda = 620$ nm, equal to 1.2 A/W. This value results to be three orders of magnitude higher than what reported in the literature for similar devices.⁵⁹ Assuming the noise to be limited by shot noise⁶⁷, the specific detectivity, D^* , of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure can be estimated using the following formula

$$D^* = \sqrt{\frac{S_{\text{active}}}{2qI_{\text{dark}}}} R$$

where q is the electron charge and I_{dark} is the dark current (measured before illumination). Based on the measured responsivity, R , the specific detectivity is on the order of 10^7 Jones with $\lambda = 620$ nm.

Figure 5: (a) Photocurrent of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar under laser at different wavelengths at $V_{\text{ds}} = 5 \text{ V}$ and $V_{\text{gs}} = -50 \text{ V}$. (b) Evolution of the photocurrent of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure at $\lambda = 620 \text{ nm}$ under pressures from high vacuum at 10^{-4} mbar to ambient pressure. The colour scale in the graph at the middle goes from 10^3 mbar (black) to 10^{-4} mbar (red).

Fixing the wavelength at $\lambda = 620 \text{ nm}$, the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure was tested as a pressure optoelectronic sensor. Figure 5b shows the evolution of the photocurrent during transitions between high vacuum (10^{-4} mbar) and ambient pressure (10^3 mbar). The half-filled squares represent the responsivity as the pressure increases from high vacuum to ambient pressure, while the filled diamonds indicate the reverse transition, from ambient pressure to high vacuum. The change in photocurrent is clearly attributed to adsorption/desorption processes occurring on the materials' surfaces, which play a crucial role in modifying the photoresponse of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterojunction. Notably, the return to the initial configuration demonstrates the stability of the materials under varying pressure conditions, highlighting their potential for sensing applications.

The adsorption process is governed by timescales that depend on the materials' structure and the nature of adsorbates. The slight jump in photocurrent at a pressure of around 10^{-2} mbar in the final stage (Figure 5b, right panel) may be attributed to a transient phase evolving between 10^{-4} and 10^{-2} mbar or to more complex mechanisms occurring in high vacuum, as previously observed in the sublinear photoresponse.⁶⁸ The evolution of the photoresponse of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterojunction under varying pressure conditions was reproduced with analogous results at $V_{\text{ds}} = -5 \text{ V}$ and $V_{\text{gs}} = -50 \text{ V}$ (see Figure S6, Supporting Information).

Conclusions

We have fabricated back-gated vdW heterostructures based on $WS_2/PdSe_2$, exfoliating single flakes and transferring them on prepatterned Si/SiO₂ substrates with Cr/Au electrodes. We have electrically characterized these devices in dark and under illumination (in different configurations) under different pressure conditions, highlighting the crucial role of adsorbates on the performance of the devices.

$WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructures are dominated by n-type conduction. The reversibility of air molecules adsorption/desorption is firstly demonstrated by repeated cycles of measurements in dark under different pressure conditions, from 10^3 to 10^{-4} mbar, and back to ambient pressure, with transfer curves that maintain an ON/OFF ratio around 10^7 - 10^8 in all the configurations.

We have investigated the photoresponse of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure and compared with single WS_2 -based devices. The photocurrent of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure at ambient pressure is one order of magnitude lower than in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar, achieving photocurrents up to the order of μA . With increasing incident laser power, the photocurrent raises sublinearly, indicating a photocurrent generation mechanism where trap states play a dominant role. This type of mechanism is generally slow, according to the extracted time constant τ_2 around 10 seconds both at ambient pressure and in high vacuum. The direct photogeneration results to be faster in high vacuum with a τ_1 about 0.2 s. These response times are faster than what achieved with single WS_2 – based FETs because of the combination of WS_2 with a semiconductor presenting a higher mobility ($PdSe_2$). The spectral photoresponse of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure was also analysed in the visible range. Remarkably, the device based on the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterojunction has been tested as a pressure optoelectronic sensor, demonstrating a fast response to light and high sensitivity to surrounding pressure conditions. These findings can appreciably contribute to the emerging field of vdW heterojunctions and the potential applications of both standard and noble-metal-based TMDs, enabling high-performance applications in electronics, optoelectronics, and sensing. Moreover, the devices were tested under high voltage biases and subjected to high currents, demonstrating their potential for real-world applications.

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Supporting Information

Van der Waals WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure as a visible-light photodetector and pressure optoelectronic sensor

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1. Optical images of steps of fabrication procedure & schematic of band diagram of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterojunction
2. AFM profiles extraction and differential reflectance spectrum of WS₂
3. Hysteresis width and ON/OFF current ratio of transfer curves of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure
4. Exponential fit of time-resolved light pulses on the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure & responsivity and detectivity as a function of incident laser power
5. Photoresponse of single WS₂-based FETs
6. Evolution of the photoresponse of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure under different pressure at negative bias voltage
7. Comparison of this work with the literature

Figure S6: Optical image of the (a) WS₂ and (b) PdSe₂ flake onto a PDMS stamp. The optical contrast gives information about the thickness and homogeneity of the materials. Optical image of the device (c) after the transfer of the first flake (WS₂) and (d) after the transfer of the second flake (PdSe₂). Optical image of the single (e) WS₂ and (f) PdSe₂ FET.

1. Optical images of steps of fabrication procedure

WS₂ and PdSe₂ flakes were obtained through mechanical exfoliation from bulk crystals by HQ Graphene onto polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamps. Then, the surface of the PDMS stamps was inspected through an optical microscope in transmission mode to identify high-quality and homogeneous flakes via optical contrast. Figure S1a shows the optical image of the WS₂ flake on a PDMS stamp, while Figure S1b depicts the optical image of the PdSe₂ film. Firstly, the WS₂ flake was transferred onto Si/SiO₂ substrate with prepatterned Cr/Au electrodes, with a portion of the flake in contact with the gold and the rest into the channel between electrodes.¹ Figure S1c displays the optical image of the substrate after the transfer of the first flake (WS₂), while Figure S1d reports the optical image of the complete device after the alignment and subsequent transfer of the PdSe₂ flake.

Figure S1e-f show an optical image of the single WS₂ and PdSe₂ flake – based devices, respectively, used for the comparison in the main text.

Figure S1g depicts a schematic of the band diagram of WS₂ and PdSe₂, referred to the vacuum level at thermal equilibrium. It is evident the formation of a type I heterojunction.

2. AFM profiles extraction and differential reflectance spectrum of WS₂

The height profile of the WS₂ flake reported in Figure 1d (left graph) is the average of multiple profiles acquired along the black dotted line in Figure S2a, indicating a thickness of approximately 2.4 nm. The height profile of the PdSe₂ flake reported in Figure 1d (right graph) is the average of multiple profiles acquired along the white dotted line in Figure S2b, indicating a thickness of

approximately 21 nm. Despite the measured thickness of the WS₂ flake, its monolayer nature is confirmed by the differential reflectance spectrum, reported in Figure S2c.²

Figure S2: Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) image of the (a) WS₂ and (b) PdSe₂ flake with a black and a white dotted line, respectively, indicating the regions from which the height profiles were extracted. (c) Differential reflectance spectrum of the WS₂ flake.

3. Hysteresis width and ON/OFF current ratio of transfer curves of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure

Figure S3a shows the transfer curve at $n = 5$ as an example, with the ON and OFF current levels indicated in blue and the maximum hysteresis width of the transfer curve marked with a green line. The hysteresis width of the transfer curves, defined as the maximum gate voltage difference between the two branches of the curve (see Figure S3a), evolves gradually across the states from $n = 1$ to $n = 5$. As depicted in Figure S3b (green dots, left axis), it decreases from 70 V at ambient pressure ($n = 1$) to 15 V at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar ($n = 3$). The ON/OFF current ratio, defined as the ratio between the maximum and minimum current of the transfer curves at different states ranges between 10^7 and 10^8 , as shown in Figure S3b (blue dots, right axis).

Figure S3: (a) Transfer curve at $n = 5$ with the ON and OFF current states indicated in blue and the hysteresis width of the transfer curve marked with a green line. (b) Evolution of the hysteresis width of the transfer curve (green dots, left axis) and ON/OFF current ratio (blue dots, right axis) across the states from $n = 1$ to $n = 5$.

4. Exponential fit of time-resolved light pulses on the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure

The time-resolved measurements under white light pulses lasting 60 seconds are well-fitted with a double exponential function. The relaxation constant times, τ_1 and τ_2 , were extracted from the double exponential fit ($I_d = I_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + A_2 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}}$) of the rise and decay branch of the pulses at ambient pressure and in high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar. Figure S4a and S4c show the fit of a pulse at ambient pressure and in high vacuum, respectively, as an example. The constant

times reported in Figure 3g and Figure 3h of the main text are the averaged values weighted with respect to their standard errors.³

The ratio between the amplitudes A_1 and A_2 of the double exponential functions provides information about the contribution of the associated mechanisms to photocurrent generation. The A_1/A_2 ratio, obtained from the double exponential fit of the pulses at ambient pressure and in high vacuum, is depicted in Figure S4b and Figure S4d, respectively. Its value close to 1 indicates a well-balanced contribution of both the mechanisms to photogeneration.

The responsivity, defined as $R = I_{ph}/P_{inc}$, where $P_{inc} = P \cdot (S_{active}/S_{spot})$ with S_{active} being the active area of the device and S_{spot} the area of the laser spot, increases significantly under high vacuum, reaching up to 12 mA/W. This represents an enhancement of nearly 20x compared to ambient conditions. As typically observed in 2D materials – based photodetectors, the responsivity decreases with increasing laser power due to saturation of trap states. Figure S4e-f (left axis) show the responsivity of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure as a function of the incident laser power, both at ambient pressure and in high vacuum conditions, at $V_{ds} = 5$ V and $V_{ds} = -5$ V. Assuming the noise to be limited by shot noise⁴, the specific detectivity, D^* , of the $WS_2/PdSe_2$ heterostructure can be estimated using the following formula

$$D^* = \sqrt{\frac{S_{active}}{2qI_{dark}}} R$$

where S_{active} is the active area of the device, q is the electron charge, I_{dark} is the dark current (measured before illumination) and R is the responsivity of the device. It is of the order of 10^5 Jones at ambient pressure, with a peak value of 4×10^5 Jones at $V_{ds} = 5$ V. This is attributed to the low dark under these conditions. Under high vacuum, however, the dark current increases (on the order of 1 μ A even in the dark), and this leads to a decrease in the specific detectivity. The dependence of the specific detectivity on the incident laser power is depicted in Figure S4e-f (right axis), both at ambient pressure and in high vacuum conditions, at $V_{ds} = 5$ V and $V_{ds} = -5$ V.

Figure S4: Light pulse under white light illumination at an incident laser power of 145 μW for 60 seconds at (a) ambient pressure and in (c) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar with the rise (black line) and decay branch (red line) fitted with a double exponential function. A_1/A_2 ratio extracted from the double exponential fits at (b) ambient pressure and in (d) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar. Responsivity (left axis) and detectivity (right axis) of the WS2/PdSe2 heterostructure at (e) ambient pressure and in (f) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar, at $V_{ds} = 5$ V and $V_{ds} = -5$ V.

5. Photoresponse of WS₂

The optoelectronic characterization of single WS₂ flakes-based FETs is reported in Figure S5. Figure S5a shows white light pulses lasting 60 seconds at ambient pressure varying the incident laser power from 33 to 163 μW. All the pulses acquired at ambient pressure were correctly fitted with a double exponential function, $I_d = I_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + A_2 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}}$, both for the rise and decay part, as depicted for the pulse at 98 μW, as an example. The extracted τ_1 and τ_2 time constants, reported in Figure S5b, are on the order of the 1 s (10 s) and 40 s (100 s), respectively, for the rise (decay) branch of the acquired light pulses at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V at ambient pressure. In Figure S5c, the analogue white light pulses in a high vacuum of 10^{-4} mbar are depicted. The rise branch of these pulses was correctly fitted with a double exponential fit with τ_1 on the order of 1 s, whereas the decay branch was fitted with a single exponential fit with τ_1 between 35 and 80 s (see Figure S5d).

Figure S5: Time-resolved measurements of single WS₂ – based FETs under white light illumination. 60 s long pulses at different incident laser powers, from 33 (red points) to 163 (blue points) μW at (a) ambient pressure and in (c) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar at $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V. Exponential fits of the rise (black line) and decay branch (red line) of the light pulses at an incident laser power of 98 μW. Time constants τ_1 and/or τ_2 from a double or single exponential fit of the time-resolved pulses at (b) ambient pressure and in (d) high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar.

6. Evolution of the photoresponse of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure under different pressure at negative bias voltage

The pressure-dependent photoresponse of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure was investigated at $\lambda = 620$ nm at $V_{ds} = -5$ V and $V_{gs} = -50$ V. Figure S6a shows the evolution of the photocurrent during the transitions between high vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-4} mbar and ambient pressure. The experimental data follows the same behaviour observed analogously at $V_{ds} = 5$ V in the main text. The smaller values of photocurrent in high vacuum, before having a pressure of 10^{-2} mbar, are attributed to not completed desorption processes. The desorption process completes on timescales longer than the ones used in that first set of measurements. A more detailed study on the timescales of adsorption/desorption can be object of future investigations. To confirm this explanation, in Figure S6b, the evolution of photocurrent of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure from high vacuum to ambient pressure at $V_{ds} = -5$ V is compared to the same acquired at $V_{ds} = 5$ V. Notably, before reaching a pressure of about 10^{-2} mbar, in both the cases a first slight jump in photocurrent can be observed before the monotonic decrease at increasing the pressure. The presence of deep and long-lived trap states contributes to this reduction and slowing of the desorption of water and oxygen molecules from the materials' surfaces.

Figure S6: (a) Evolution of the photocurrent of the WS₂/PdSe₂ heterostructure at $\lambda = 620$ nm under pressures from high vacuum at 10^{-4} mbar to ambient pressure at $V_{ds} = -5$ V and $V_{gs} = -50$ V. (b) Comparison of photocurrent as a function of the pressure from high vacuum at 10^{-4} mbar to ambient pressure at $V_{ds} = -5$ V (black dots) and $V_{ds} = 5$ V (red dots).

7. Comparison of this work with the literature

The comparison of our results with what reported in the literature is summarized in the following table.

	WS ₂ thickness (nm)	PdSe ₂ thickness (nm)	Conductive behaviour	On/off current ratio	V _{ds} (V)	Responsivity (A/W)	α ($I_{ph} \propto P^\alpha$)
10.1002/adom.202001991⁵	0.74	3.30	Ambipolar	10 ³	0.6	4 x 10 ⁻³ [at 635 nm]	0.76 [at 635 nm]
10.1007/s40843-024-2944-0⁶	8	10	Ambipolar	10 ⁵	1	Not investigated	Not investigated
This work.	2.4*	21	n-type	10 ⁷	5	1.2 [at 620 nm]	(0.71 ± 0.07) [at V _{ds} = 5 V] (0.88 ± 0.06) [at V _{ds} = -5 V]

* Despite the measured thickness (2.4 nm) of the WS₂ flake, the position of the two characteristic peaks of the Raman spectrum of the WS₂ flake suggests that the WS₂ flake is a monolayer.

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